

A Framework for Categorizing Talent Management System Benefits

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Abstract— The talent management systems (TMS) represent an integrated set of analytical tools for the creation and management of talent knowledge in organizations. Several such systems, available from various vendors, aims to support the strategic imperatives of organizations by providing a number of benefits. Backtracking into the available evidence, however, suggests that such benefits from TMS are often stated in a generic way, presented in an unstructured manner, and are at different levels of abstractions thereby making an assessment of such benefits difficult. The study, based on an analysis of practitioners' interviews, offers a categorization of the TMS benefits in five dimensions along with possible benefit indicators and select example metrics. The categorization is expected to assist practitioners in developing a basis for planning for TMS implementation, establishing benchmarks for effective TMS implementation, and facilitating comparisons between expected and realized benefits. Some theoretical contributions are also possible which are also delineated.

Keywords— Talent Management Systems, Benefit Assessment, Qualitative Research

I. INTRODUCTION

Ever since 1998, when a group of consultants from McKinsey coined the expression “war for talent” and posited that a fundamental belief in the importance of talent is needed to achieve organizational excellence [1], talent management has been an increasingly popular topic [2]. In recent years, a notable increase in the number of articles and books relating to talent management could be observed as it is seen more and more as a high-priority issue for organizations worldwide [3]. Proper talent management is considered a critical determinant of organizational success [4], and imperative for the livelihood and sustainability of organizations [5].

The developments related to talent management also let to conceptualizations of systems that can facilitate processes related to talent management in organizations. The talent management systems (TMS) which resulted from such endeavours represented an integrated set of analytical tools for the creation and management of talent knowledge [6]. Belonging to the class of enterprise systems (ES)¹, TMS are extensions of competency management systems (i.e. systems which facilitate workforce planning in organizations) to include functions that identify critical roles and tasks and supply crucial competency development actions for certain target groups, so-called talents [7]. With growing needs, several such talent management systems came into existence, created by different vendors, to support the talent management needs of organizations [8].

With the talent management function having already gained strategic importance, investments in TMS are often driven by corporate-level agendas to achieve competitive advantage in the market [9]. Along with this, there are manifold expectations of benefits from its use. Understanding of the benefits is considered to be instrumental in assessing TMS success, while a low awareness of the benefits can act as an impediment towards realizing the full potential out of such systems. The primary objectives of why organizations need a TMS are to automate and streamline the entire talent management process and provide useful analytics and feedback to help management [10]. However, the benefits of using TMS are mentioned in various sources in an unstructured manner. This complicates an assessment of the benefits and the way it may be contributing to the organizational goals. The categorization which we offer in this paper identifies and categorizes the TMS benefits, provides indicators for each benefit dimension, and

¹ Enterprise systems are large-scale, real-time, integrated application-software packages that use the computational, data storage, and data transmission technology to support processes, information flows, reporting, and business analytics within and between complex organizations (Seddon et al. 2010).

indicates example metrics for specific indicators. The categorization is expected to assist practitioners in developing a basis for planning for TMS implementation, establishing benchmarks for effective TMS implementation, and facilitating comparisons between expected and realized benefits. The presentation is also expected to provide researchers with a systematic approach for exploring TMS benefits.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Talent Management Systems

Talent management systems (TMS) refer to information systems (IS) that include features designed to help organizational employees reach their full potential and to keep the organizational leadership well-informed of their performance. The need for TMS was realized with the gradual move towards the automation of manual human resource (HR) processes. Figure 1 shows the elements of a typical TMS which includes the following elements: need (refers to the business needs derived from the business model and competitive issues), data collection (identifies the fundamental data and “intelligence” critical for good talent decisions), planning (refers to people/talent planning guided by data analysis), activity (indicates the conversion of plans into integrated sets of activities), and results (costs, measures, and effectiveness criteria to judge the value and impacts of talent management) [11]. Such a unified TMS can contribute effectively towards organizational causes based on anticipating and predicting talent needs and providing required analytics and dashboard enabled by futuristic technologies (e.g., artificial intelligence (AI) and analytics, machine learning) [12, 13].

Fig. 1 Elements of a Typical Talent Management System [11]

The existing academic research on TMS introduces these systems and describe aspects specific to these systems, for example, the structure (e.g. elements of TMS), functionalities (e.g. what is the system expected to do), evolution (e.g. how the systems have evolved in several stages over the years), integration aspects (which can be the integration of TMS as various systems may provide different capabilities, or the integration of TMS with other related information systems like HR systems, decision support systems) (e.g., Birchall et al. [14]; Faqihi and Miah [15]; Zielinski [16]).

B. TMS Benefit Assessment

IS benefit assessment methods help us in understanding how the information systems are able to satisfy the objectives of an organization. The scope of IS benefit assessment is dependent upon various factors like the context of decision making and requirements of the IS under consideration [17]. Organizations invest in information systems to eventually realize benefits from the successful implementation. The benefits can be towards solving a specific problem or for identifying an innovative solution. Organizations investing on a large scale to achieve some benefits also need clear methods to evaluate or measure those benefits [18].

The importance of TMS in the present context makes it more necessary to understand how we assess (what) benefits are realized from the use of these systems in organizations. The existing inquiries on TMS have not quite paid attention to this concern as the role of TMS could have been viewed as facilitating management of talent and hence the benefits can be assumed to be implied. There are scattered reports on benefits to organizations from using TMS available on various websites. For example, ELMO [19] reports that the seven ways in which TMS can benefit an organization are 1. Connecting and sharing data, 2. Strategic hiring process, 3. Improved onboarding experience, 4. Retain top talent, 5. Employee development, 6. Improved employee experience, and 7. Increased employee and manager engagement. Quirk [20] lists the top five benefits of TMS as 1. improved hiring techniques, 2. Easily develop employees, 3. Access to accurate data, 4. Improved cultural connections and employee engagement, and 5. Retain top talent. Likewise, Mohapatra [21] identifies nine reasons why an organization should invest in TMS as 1. Find ideal professionals for the right roles, 2. Impassion your staff, 3. Empower performance consistency, 4. Distinguish and close hierarchical talent gaps, 5. Retain already present and recently hired top talent, 6. Aim for fewer hiring-related errors during the recruitment process, 7. Better understanding of the workforce, 8. Make employees feel valued and motivated, and 9. Build trust in your organization. There are plenty of other website sources that also report benefits of TMS for organizations and practitioners with the identified points either complementing the existing entries or building to it. In a nutshell, the TMS benefit is expected to assist one to understand to what degree the talent management goals of an organization are achieved. This is difficult to assess as the benefits listed in the different sources accessible are stated in a generic way, presented in an unstructured manner, and are also at different level of granularities (for example some benefit item may be at an organizational level, (i.e. organizational trust) while some may be attributes of employees (employee experience).

Currently, there are a lot of confusion in organizations related to what metrics should be tracked for talent management process and system benefits, thereby driving efficiency and effectiveness within organizations. Focusing on benefits like cost reduction drive the focus on reducing time to hire and unutilized talents by deployment time as a metric. On the contrary, focus on revenue increase as benefits of TMS shift the focus towards predictive analytics and planning for the future while giving less importance to immediate cost. There are also benefits that relate to a better experience for the employees and benefits leading to better empowerment for the managers. As practitioners, these contradictions and possibilities make us wary of whether there is a right balance at all for an organization. Every organization has its goal and hence there is a need to effectively track the benefits that may be realized out of the extant systems (i.e. TMS) to justify the presence of such systems within the organization. A framework that can allow categorization of the TMS benefits suitably is likely to be useful in this regard. Identifying and structuring the TMS benefits may not only permit an assessment of the TMS potential but can also pave the way for better realization of these intended benefits. Acknowledging the need for a structured assessment of TMS benefits, in this endeavor, we adopt a framework to identify and categorize the TMS benefits into specified dimensions which we discuss below.

III. GUIDING FRAMEWORK

Shang and Seddon [22] based on a review of 233 ERP (Enterprise resource planning) system success stories proposed the following five benefit categories (Table I) for a holistic assessment of ES benefits.

TABLE I
ES BENEFIT DIMENSIONS [22]

Dimension	Interpretations
Operational benefits	Operational activities process day-to-day activities that involve acquiring and consuming resources. The activities are usually repeated periodically, such as daily, weekly and monthly.
Managerial benefits	Business management activities involve allocation and control of the firm's resources, monitoring of operations and supporting of business strategic decisions.
Strategic benefits	Strategic activities are actions that are related to organization's efforts in maintaining and creating competitive advantage.
IT Infrastructure benefits	IT (Information Technology) infrastructure consists of sharable and reusable IT resources that provide a foundation for business applications.
Organizational benefits	Organizational benefits arise when the use of an ES benefits an organization in terms of focus, cohesion, learning and execution of its chosen strategies.

The framework provides segregation of benefits in five dimensions that may be achievable using ES. The authors report that benefits realization is an ongoing process, with benefits in each of the five dimensions being realized at different rates in different core processes in different organizations. However, it may not be expected that all organizations will achieve benefits in all five main dimensions. We use this guiding framework as the starting artifact to structure TMS benefits. The mapping of the TMS benefits along the framework dimensions and further operationalizing them can reveal the state of TMS benefits and assist in driving initiatives towards realizing organizational objectives.

IV. STUDY METHOD

Semi-structured interviews following an interview guide were carried out with 15 practitioners having considerable experiences with talent management systems. They represented middle and senior-level management positions in organizations belonging to different industry sectors (Consumer Discretionary – 3, Consumer Staples – 1, Financials – 3, Health Care – 1, IT – 5, Manufacturing – 1, Real Estate - 1). The interviews, each mostly lasting around one hour and a half, were carried out in-person or over the telephone. To analyze the interview content, we used the data analysis process by Yin [23] comprising of familiarization, transcription, organization of data, coding the data, building the description and themes, and finally writing the report. To build the themes and code, we followed the framework based analysis recommendations [24]. Here an initial organizing framework serves as a basis to analyze the content. The framework allows the categories and themes to be set accordingly from the beginning of any study. The set of initial categories for our study were adapted from Shang and Seddon [22]. During the coding process using Ms. Excel, any new themes that emerged were subsequently added in the hierarchical tree of themes, leading to the findings.

V. FINDINGS

A. Nature of TMS

The interviewees were asked about the TMS that are in use in their respective organizations. Some interviewees also provided views on multiple TMS based on their past experiences. TMS in use in organizations ranged from major ERPs like SAP, Oracle to niche systems like Cornerstone to custom-built applications in some. The major ERP vendors (e.g. products of SAP, Oracle) were noted to be having the

best capability in the TMS till date. Some interviewees felt that Oracle had an initial advantage of better functionality due to earlier entry into the space of HR after the acquisition of Peoplesoft. However, that advantage was nullified once SAP acquired SuccessFactors.

B. TMS Benefits

We integrate the findings from the interviews with the TMS benefits documented in the literature following Shang and Seddon's [22] ES benefit dimensions' framework, which we discuss below and finally summarize in Table II at the end of this section.

Operational Benefits:

Many interviewees were able to provide insights on how TMS assist in driving operational benefits in the organization. One interviewee mentioned, "*Automated integrated systems to track talent supply and demands have helped to reduce the team [size] that manages the talent planning and deployment*". This represented an instance where the reduced size of the HR team engaged in the staffing function resulted in a (direct) cost reduction benefit. Another interviewee indicated, "*With organizational-wide visibility to talent availability, we have been able to improve the talent utilization from below 80% to over 85%. This has significantly reduced the bench cost.*" Here talent utilization was suggested as a direct measure of cost reduction. The term bench cost, typically used in sectors like IT and ITES (Information Technology Enabled Services), refers to talents not presently engaged in projects.

Cycle time reduction was another operational benefit that was recognized by the interviewees. This was primarily attributed to the metrics associated with the recruitment function such as reduced time to hire and improved onboarding process [20], reduction in time to fill-up positions, and an overall reduction in closure time for performance and CNB (compensation and benefits) cycles which earlier used to take a lot of time with manual follow-ups. Interviewees indicated that earlier appraisal and CNB closure was time-consuming as it took a lot of time to collate, normalize and sanitize data. This is now greatly facilitated by the ability of TMS to connect and share data across the entire system [19]. An interviewee summed up the cycle time reduction benefits nicely in his comments as "*... if I compare 2 cycles, it will be 60-70 days reduction. It is a great improvement.*"

Productivity improvements by the use of TMS were also noticed. To quote an interviewee, "*... automation in workforce planning ... [related processes] has significantly helped gain efficiencies, reduced manual and arduous tasks, simplified the processes and has aided in the standardization of the processes across departments.*" A comparison of the number of people in HR or talent function before and after TMS introduction was referred to as a measure of such improvements, as per the respondent.

Quality improvements represented the next set of gains from using TMS. The interviewees concurred on a noticeable improvement in the quality of data [20] since the use of integrated systems for talent management. TMS facilitated recruiting quality talents by streamlining the hiring process and allowing more time to focus on the candidates [19]. Quality of hire or talents recruited to an organization can be traced easily via integrated recruitment, onboarding and performance management systems. The interviewees felt that the real-time availability of accurate data has improved the overall quality of all relevant processes. It was also possible to reduce inadvertent errors during the hiring process [21].

Managerial Benefits:

Improved resource management is enabled by TMS. Better visibility of organizational-wide data facilitates the organization in addressing critical resource allocation and management issues on a real-time basis [21]. The system facilitates the management to better understand employees' skills from the appraisals. This can further assist in planning promotion structures as the management can better recognize the requirements, professional goals and qualities, and also the shortcomings of the talents [21]. The benefits to resource allocation were also apparent in the following quote from an interviewee, "*... online*

system to track the current status of each talent gives current availability. The system captures who is working on what project and is likely to work in that project for how long. We can plan for their next assignment even before they come to [the] bench.” Another interviewee added “An IT system with a centralized database is immensely helpful for consolidating and collating data. This goes a long way in finding and matching resources ... Also, the comments like location constraints, etc. are captured and visible.” Location constraints mentioned in the quote implies that for each talent in the organization, there is clear tracking enabled for aspirations (role, location of posting, etc.) along with skills to match requirements to talents. TMS also facilitates closing hierarchical talent gaps fast by distinguishing them early [21].

Decision making is improved in the presence of historical and current data. In this regard, in the context of using a dashboard for decision making while referring to the SAP SuccessFactors, an interviewee quoted: “... the biggest benefit is that everything is attached to analytics, so they have a central analytics tool that pulls data from talent management, recruitment [modules] and all. It can correlate all the data and populate the dashboard automatically.”

Performance improvement processes in terms of employee appraisals are easily traceable in the TMS to compare year on year improvement. The system enables “continuous feedback” which provides visibility to performance achievement and improvement, thereby facilitating employee development [19, 20]. In the words of an interviewee “It has helped in keeping a log of journal entries, making the end of year appraisals/reviews a much smoother process. We do not have to try and remember at the end of the year what the employee did 10-11 months back. This helps us focus on our core processes.”

Strategic Benefits:

Linkage of organizational goals with the individual talent goals in the performance management process was observed to be facilitated in the presence of TMS. An interviewee quoted the following as a support of this observation: “An employee can see how my x goal contributes to the company goal. As an employee, I can see my company goal. I can see how my contribution is going to company performance.” To further clarify this point, an employee may not have access to the TMS systems of the organization; however, the HR personnel in charge (and using the TMS) can facilitate such a vision.

The interviewees differed on their viewpoint of the contribution of the TMS at the strategic level. Several interviewees pointed out the present systems are still not contributing as much in the strategic space. An interviewee mentioned, “Right now I do not think the system is impacting any of the strategic benefits. However, a system has the potential to impact the above if it is integrated well.” Several interviewees opined that TMS is more a “reflector of business” than a “director of business”. These phrases indicate that the business strategies currently direct talent strategy and talent decisions. TMS is just an enabler of such downstream processes. The systems do not influence business strategies in most of the cases.

There were expectations that TMS should “move from [being] a transaction management (processing) system to the upper layers of the pyramid”. The need for TMS to contribute to the strategic needs and be more “intelligent” resonated with the idea of “AI [Artificial Intelligence] for TMS” as one interviewee indicated that agility enabled by better data availability can actually facilitate business planning activities.

IT Infrastructure Benefits:

Not many citations on IT infrastructure benefits could be obtained from the interviews. Some interviewees referred to the scalability feature of TMS as a sub-dimension of IT infrastructure benefits. Building business flexibility for current and future changes was another benefit belonging to this category which was recognized. There have been new requirements in terms of global accessibility, language requirements in the presence of a global workforce. In words of an interviewee: “We have global data in one system. Global data is present in one system plus we are able to apply all the processes consistently.”

Building systems that are mobile-accessible are a need of the day. Almost all organizations are now moving from premise-based infrastructure to cloud infrastructure. The capability of TMS to attune to these changes is a benefit perceived by some.

Organizational Benefits:

In terms of organizational benefits, TMS contributed to a greater adaptation to changing work patterns to some extent. This reflected in the following quote from an interviewee: *“we are able to tap into talents across locations to staff specific skills ... leading to more diverse teams that come together to deliver and have an agile distributed workforce.”*

Further, a TMS can also drive organizational learning by providing insights into potential future skills. An interviewee corroborated this as *“... analysis of changing demands over the years gives insight into evolving technologies so that decisions can be taken to reskill talents into these emerging technologies.”* TMS also facilitate talents to choose a career path from available opportunities via channels such as IJPs (internal job postings) etc. These talents can have access to internal job opportunities and various career paths and the presence of a TMS greatly facilitates these processes.

TMS can lead to better engagement between the management and the staff and lead to their empowerment. The system facilitates staff and managers to interact with the staff's professional career progression while also focusing on their personal goals [19]. It is now possible for the employees to decide in advance or even in real-time which training to attend, what performance appraisal feedback to work on, etc. Employees, especially the younger ones, are also more inclined to operate within established hierarchies when they understand where they are needed and where they might be headed [21]. The employees also now have more clarity regarding compensation and other benefits/incentives regarding how these are determined, The access to appraisal ratings and feedback ahead of critical decisions like compensation and benefits have all contributed to empowering employees which is a form of information empowerment rather than psychological. All these will contribute to impassioning the workforce and making the employees feel valued and motivated [21].

There is also evidence of greater employee accountability in presence of TMS. The presence of the system results in transparency as one interviewee commented: *“... in a system, there is more transparency. One can see what happened last year, this year. ... As an employee, I get to see what are the consistent development areas”*. With clarity, the employees will have greater trust in the organization and its objectives [21]. The outcome of this is a pool of talent that is locked in, dedicated and resolved to do what is best for the organization's success.

The interviewees also observed that TMS can contribute to better employee morale and satisfaction with some indicating faster response time to resolution of employee issues (e.g. in the context of employee grievance handling) as a possible metric for measuring the same. Satisfaction can result from improved employee experience as it can permit the employees to handle tasks like access to payslip, leave requests and management, etc. hassle-free. Organizational charts can also be included, letting employees know the reporting and management structure of the organization [19]. Further, with the entire employee information hosted on one platform, TMS assist the organization in closely monitoring top talents already present to ensure they are happy and on the right track [19, 21]. In this way, the TMS also facilitate the organization in addressing the employee needs.

TABLE III
TMS BENEFIT CATEGORIZATION

Operational Benefits: Cost Reduction, Cycle Time Reduction, Productivity Improvement, Quality Improvement	Managerial Benefits: Improved Resource Management, Better Decision Making, Performance Improvement
Strategic Benefits: Improved Business Goals Mapping	IT Infrastructure Benefits: Improved Scalability of Operations, Greater Flexibility of Systems
Organizational Benefits: Changing Work Patterns, Facilitating Organizational Learning, Greater Employee Accountability, Increased Employee Engagement and Empowerment, Better Employee Morale and Satisfaction	

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study based on an analysis of 15 interviews identifies and categorizes the TMS benefits in five dimensions following the Shang and Seddon [22] ES benefit dimensions' framework. The benefits were identified from both an analysis of existing evidence and the interview contents involving experienced practitioners belonging to different industry sectors. The categorization of the TMS benefits in an overall simple structure provides researchers and practitioners with a systematic approach to understanding TMS benefits. The interviews also revealed example metrics for certain benefit indicators to facilitate the application of these in theory and practice. The findings largely suggest that, in contradiction with TMS investment intentions, the predominant usage of TMS is mostly at the operational and the tactical levels. However, future expectations that the TMS will actually transcend to the strategic levels were echoed. Some interesting viewpoints were also noted. Some interviewees stressed that no system can change organizational learning, or innovation or strategy. Quoting one interviewee verbatim: *"All the strategy, everything will happen through human beings [interventions]. It is [the] human beings who will look into the system and improvise and make it relevant."* Our explorations are not yet complete with more practitioner interviews across some other industry sectors planned in the coming weeks. On completion, the analysis (of the new content) will be integrated with the present report.

The expected contributions of our work hold promise for both practice and theory. From a practical perspective, the findings are expected to be useful to organizations implementing TMS. The categorization of TMS benefits is expected to provide a basis for planning for TMS implementation and also for establishing benchmarks for effective TMS implementation. It may be possible for organizations to customize the benefits depending upon whether the entire TMS or only select modules are chosen for implementation. This may pave way for a tiered implementation based on the maturity of the TMS rather than module-based implementation as is currently prevalent. Establishing a customized set of expected benefits can also pave the way for a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis to determine the usefulness of TMS to an organization. The proposed categorization may also be used in conducting post-TMS implementation reviews which can enable comparison of expected and realized benefits out of the system. Our categorization is also expected to serve as a database representing possible benefit dimensions that may be realized from a TMS and used for benchmarking activities while planning new TMS. The expected contributions of this study to the theory are a greater understanding of TMS which are still in infancy in terms of integration and contribution to organizational objectives. Our proposed categorization offers researchers with a systematic approach for exploring TMS benefits, which can be used in other related empirical studies. Refinement of the categorization, once finalized, is possible using the Delphi Study approach to capture the perceptions of a larger number of talent management experts. The final results may also provide a sound basis for further research that explores the gap between expected and realized benefits in TMS. It may also be possible to develop an instrument to measure net benefits realized using TMS, and perhaps establish baselines for particular industry sectors. The comprehensive listing of

TMS benefit indicators and associated metrics are expected to provide a starting point for the development of the instrument.

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